

Achieving climate neutrality targets decision support system

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*D4.1. List of tools and instruments for potential
application CLIMA-SIM-LV*

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**D.4.1 List of tools and instruments for potential application CLIMA-SIM-LV,
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1 INTRODUCTION

To analyse the different possible pathways towards climate neutrality, a variety of advanced modelling tools and instruments are used to simulate and analyse the impacts of policies and measures on energy systems, emissions, land use and the economy. These tools and instruments provide a comprehensive view, integrating economic, demographic and environmental data, thus offering future scenarios and the ability to assess the effectiveness of different strategies. They allow policy makers to assess the impact of energy and environmental policies, explore options for reducing greenhouse gas emissions and understand the trade-offs and co-benefits of different mitigation measures. By modelling the interactions between human activities and natural systems, these tools support informed decision-making for sustainable development, green energy transition and climate resilience at national and regional level. Through scenario analysis and policy assessments, they help develop effective strategies to meet climate targets and long-term sustainability goals.

The set of modelling tools and instruments selected for potential application in the CLIMA-SIM-LV is a diverse range of sophisticated tools designed to address different aspects of environmental policy analysis.

The aim of this task is to provide a compilation of these tools in the form of a list, which can be further used for its detailed assessment in WP D4.2.

2 METHODS

A comprehensive search of various academic and professional databases was carried out to identify modelling tools and instruments. Resources such as *Google Scholar*, *Scopus* and *Web of Science* were used to find peer-reviewed articles and reports on existing tools. The search was refined using keywords such as "*GHG emission modelling tools*", "*carbon calculators*" and "*GHG mitigation tools*". In addition, literature from international organisations such as the IPCC, UNFCCC, FAO and the European Environment Agency was reviewed to provide a broader understanding of the tools available.

3 RESULTS

The Table 2 summarises the information on the identified tools in the form of a list, with the full name and description of the tool, as well as the developer and the reference of the scientific publication. These tools and instruments provide a comprehensive overview of GHG emission calculations and assessments in the sectors defined in the project, modelling the impact of different policies. Importantly, they also offer future scenarios and the possibility to assess the effectiveness of different strategies by integrating economic, demographic and environmental data. They allow policy makers to assess the impact of energy and environmental policies, explore options for reducing greenhouse gas emissions and understand the trade-offs and co-benefits of different mitigation measures

Table 2. List of summary information on identified tools and instruments

Nr.	Name of tools and instruments	Description	Developer, references
1.	PRIMES	Modelling energy markets and assessing the impact of energy policies in the EU	E3-Modelling, Greece https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2018.06.016
2.	GAINS (Greenhouse Gas and Air Pollution Interactions and Synergies)	Assess emissions of air pollutants and greenhouse gases and their impacts on health, ecosystems and climate	International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis, Austria https://doi.org/10.1088/2515-7620/ab7457
3.	GLOBIOM-G4M	Combines models from the agriculture and forestry sectors to analyse global land-use dynamics and their impact on carbon sequestration and emissions.	International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis, Austria https://pure.iiasa.ac.at/16091
4.	CAPRI (Common Agricultural Policy Regional Impact Analysis)	Analyse the impact of agricultural policy on production, incomes and the environment in the EU	Consortium of European research institutions, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2006.10.002
5.	MAGNET	Analyse the impact of agricultural, trade and environmental policies on the world economy, land use and natural resources	Wageningen Economic Research and partners, The Netherlands https://edepot.wur.nl/310764
6.	CLUE	Modelling land-use change based on socio-economic and biophysical factors to assess the impact of land-use	Environmental Systems Analysis Group at Wageningen University, The Netherlands https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3800(94)00151-0

		policies on environmental and socio-economic outcomes.	
7.	FAST-GHG	A fertiliser and soil analysis tool designed to help quantify GHG emissions from crop production	Cornell University, USA, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2020.102952 Tonitto, C., Woodbury, P., & Woolf, D. (2020, December). Greenhouse Gas (GHG) Accounting in Agricultural Supply Chains. In <i>AGU Fall Meeting Abstracts</i> (Vol. 2020, pp. GC012-05).
8.	Agriculture and Land Use (ALU) Software	Calculate GHG emissions from agricultural land	Colorado State University, USA https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2006.03.028
9.	Ex-Ante Carbon-balance Tool (EX-ACT)	Calculate GHG emissions from agricultural land	FAO. http://www.fao.org/3/a-i8075e.pdf
10.	Cool Farm Tool	Assess the carbon footprint of agricultural practices (at farm level), including livestock farming	University of Aberdeen, Scotland https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2011.03.014
11.	Farm Carbon Calculator	Assess GHG emissions from agricultural practices (at farm level), including livestock farming	Farm Carbon Toolkit, United Kingdom https://www.farmcarbontoolkit.org.uk/toolkit/soil-carbon-emissions
12.	GHG Protocol Agricultural Guidance	Provides guidelines for GHG emissions accounting in agriculture	World Resources Institute (WRI), World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD) Protocol, G. G. (2011). Greenhouse gas protocol. <i>Sector Toolsets for Iron and Steel-Guidance Document</i> , 1-12.
13.	Dairy Greenhouse Gas Accounting Framework (D-GAF)	Calculate GHG emissions from dairy farming	Primary Industries Climate Challenges Centre (PICCC), Australia https://doi.org/10.9775/kvfd.2013.9691
14.	RothC (Rothamsted Carbon) Model	Simulates carbon cycling in soils above the groundwater (not waterlogged)	Rothamsted Research, United Kingdom, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2011.11.005

			https://doi.org/10.1007/s10666-016-9536-0
15.	DNDC (DeNitrification-DeComposition) Model	Simulate carbon and nitrogen biochemical processes in agroecosystems	University of New Hampshire, USA https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2014.09.004 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2013.01.005
16.	ORCHIDEE (Organizing Carbon and Hydrology In Dynamic Ecosystems) Model	Simulates surface flows of carbon, water and energy	Institute Pierre Simon Laplace, France https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-11-497-2018 https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-12-4751-2019
17.	EPIC (Environmental Policy Integrated Climate) Model	Simulates the effects of soil erosion, tillage and climate change on crop productivity and soil carbon	USDA Agricultural Research Service, USA https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2005.07.010 https://epicapex.tamu.edu/media/pkknpkjt/winepic0810manual.pdf
18.	Yasso Model	Simulates the decomposition of organic matter and the dynamics of soil organic carbon stocks in forest ecosystems (but not only)	Finnish Forest Research Institute (Metla), Finland https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2005.03.005 https://lufb.ltu.lv/conference/Research-for-Rural-Development/2017/LatviaResRuralDev_23rd_2017_vol1-28-34.pdf
19.	CENTURY Model	Simulate carbon, nitrogen, phosphorus and sulphur dynamics in different ecosystems	Natural Resource Ecology Laboratory, Colorado State University, USA https://doi.org/10.1016/S0038-0717(01)00189-4 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2009.05.005
20.	CCLUB (Carbon Calculator for Land Use and Land Management Change from Biofuels Production) Model	Simulates GHG emissions based on land use and land-use change, under biofuel production scenarios	Argonne National Laboratory, USA https://www.osti.gov/biblio/1825926

21.	1.5°C national pathway explorer	Analysis of national emission flows for 64 countries (LV not included) to meet the Paris Agreement targets. There is an overall EU assessment (energy, transport, industry)	Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research et.al., Germany https://1p5ndc-pathways.climateanalytics.org/
22.	WasteMAP	CH4 emissions calculations from different types of CSA treatment	RMI https://wastemap.earth
23.	Solid Waste Emissions Estimation Tool (SWEET)	Emission calculations in the municipal waste sector. It is possible to define a baseline scenario and analyse 4 alternative scenarios	USA EPA https://www.ccacoalition.org/resources/solid-waste-emissions-estimation-tool-sweet
24.	Waste Management Assessment and Action Plan Tool	A general tool for activities and planning for more efficient waste management	https://2050today.org/climate-action-waste-management/
25.	SWM-GHG Calculator	GHG calculations according to IPCC guidelines, Life Cycle Assessment analysis.	IFEU https://www.ifeu.de/en/project/tool-for-calculating-greenhouse-gases-ghg-in-solid-waste-management-swm
26.	Waste Emissions Calculator	CO2 emissions calculations for different management practices; carbon footprint calculation, Tier3	Cambridgeshire County Council https://localpartnerships.gov.uk/resources/waste-emissions-calculator/
27.	OrganEcs	Organic waste management (i.e. composting and anaerobic digestion)	USA EPA https://www.globalmethane.org/resources/details.aspx?resourceid=5175
28.	The Freight Greenhouse Gas (GHG) Calculator	Aviation and shipping, logistics chains	https://changing-transport.org/publications/the-freight-greenhouse-gas-ghg-calculator/
29.	VECTO	CO2 emissions and fuel consumption from trucks, buses and coaches with a gross vehicle weight exceeding 3500 kg	JRC https://code.europa.eu/groups/vecto/-/wikis/home

30.	GHG Emissions Calculation Tool: Transport Tool	Calculating CO2 emissions in the transport sector	UK DEFRA https://ghgprotocol.org/calculation-tools-and-guidance
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4 CONCLUSIONS

The preliminary list of climate neutrality tools and instruments shows the importance of choosing tools that not only provide accurate and relevant data, but also align with national strategies and sectoral priorities.

Task D4.2 will include a detailed assessment of these tools and instruments, as well as an evaluation of their potential use in the CLIMA-SIM-LV system dynamics model.

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